
CSR in the marketing dimension: How do companies use their CSR approach to strengthen their brand image?

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Abstract :

In the context of globalization, the concept of corporate responsibility has evolved rapidly, under the impetus of civil society organizations, to encourage companies to review their practices and take into account the ecological and societal aspect in their strategies, which has given rise to what is known as social or responsible marketing. The objective of this article is to understand the impact of Lydec's CSR approach on its brand image, through a literature study dealing with CSR, sustainable development, responsible marketing and brand image as a first step, and as a second step a qualitative study in order to better understand the impact of this approach on its brand image.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, social marketing, branding, responsible marketing, sustainable development.

1. Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), originally defined by Bowen in 1953, encompasses all activities carried out by companies with the aim of adhering to the principles of sustainable development, intended to be economically efficient while having a positive impact on society and showing greater respect for the environment. As a result, since the Brundtland report in 1987 then the Rio conference in 1992, several countries have implemented regulations that will lay the foundations of modern CSR and several companies are now forced to invest in CSR, which is also a communication and development tool for companies. In addition, social or responsible marketing allows the company to implicitly develop a positive institutional image in the eyes of the community and therefore influences consumer behavior (Andreasen, 1994).

Our article deals with the case of Lydec. It is a water and electricity company operating in the Casablanca-Mohammedia cities, and which attributes to itself the "responsible" status, undertakes societal actions and includes respect for the environment in its strategies.

The objective of our research is to explore the perceptions of Casablanca citizens about the societal and ecological actions of Lydec and to identify what kind of image they have about it. This will allow us to assess the impact of Lydec's CSR practices on its brand image. To do this, it will first be necessary to assess the degree of knowledge of customers of this CSR approach, what are their perceptions and what opinion do they build on the company after learning about its societal and ecological actions.

Therefore, our research question is as follows: from a responsible marketing perspective, how does Lydec use its CSR approach to strengthen its brand image?

Our study was carried out through semi-directive individual interviews which relate to the themes of sustainable development, CSR and Lydec's CSR approach, aimed at identifying the perceptions of the customers interviewed on Casablanca about the latter.

In order to provide some answers to this question, our article is structured in two main axes: The first axis consists of a literature review dealing with the following concepts: CSR, sustainable development, responsible marketing and brand image. The second axis presents the results of our qualitative study in order to better understand the impact of Lydec's CSR approach on its brand image. The document is summarized by a work of synthesis and recommendations.

2. Theoretical basis

2.1. Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

In recent years, debates dealing with corporate social responsibility (CSR) have imposed themselves in the economic, political and social arenas, in both national and international settings (Batellier and Rauffet, 2012), introducing the notion of ethics in the various internal processes of company management, and the notion of responsibility towards society, through actions undertaken by the organization in question creating added value of a social nature, aimed at improving the social state.

The concept of CSR appears for the first time in the management literature “the social responsibilities of the businessman” (Bowen, 1953). The transposition of the principles of sustainable development for companies was popularized by John Elkington in 1994 with the notion of "triple bottom line", which consists in taking into account in the last line of the income statement the performance of the company in terms of the 3P (for people, planet and profit) (Leblanc and Baddache, 2015). The 2000s witnessed an intensification of the legal terms regarding companies' requirements for transparency in terms of their environmental and social data.

The Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) closely involves the application of the principles of sustainable development by companies. In other words, the company must, beyond its own economic considerations, plan and limit its impact on the environment and the social system. As a result, it must take into account the various agents in its system, which are also called stakeholders, and which include its employees, its shareholders, its consumers, its suppliers and more generally civil society, of which the NGOs are the spokespersons” (Gicquel, 2007).

Social responsibility also refers to sustainable development and corporate governance. It is first of all an attitude, a state committing to sustainable development and to taking into account a plurality of points of view. Sustainable development is a concept derived from the bio-economy (Clark, 1989): it is necessary to allow a joint evolution of economic dynamics and ecological dynamics and this results in a set of prudent practices that are applied at the global level to preservation and regeneration of natural resources (Noël, 2004).

2.2. Contributions of different authors on the subject of CSR

The table below includes different contributions of many authors in terms of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Tchankam and Estay, 2004):

Table 1: Contributions of different authors on the subject of CSR

Authors	Contribution
Davis K., 1960	Corporate social responsibility concerns the actions and decisions that businessmen take for reasons that go, in part, beyond the purely technical and economic interests of the company.
Frederick W.C., 1960	Social responsibility implies a civic attitude towards economic and human resources, and a willingness to use these resources to achieve higher social goals and not simply the narrowly circumscribed interest of a private person or a company.
McGuire J.C., 1964	The idea of social responsibility supposes that the company does not only have legal or economic obligations, but that it also has responsibilities towards society, which go beyond these obligations.
Davis k. & Bolstrom R.L., 1966	Social responsibility refers to the obligation for a person to take into account the effect of his decisions on the social system taken as a whole, businessmen exercise their responsibility when they consider the needs and interests of those who can be affected by their actions.
Walton C.C., 1967	The concept of social responsibility recognizes the intimacy of the relationship between business and society and affirms that these relationships must be present in the minds of the top managers of the company, as well as in the minds of those who take care of the different groups to which it is connected and which pursue their own goals.
Thompson S.C., 1997	The objectives pursued in the name of corporate social responsibility are those closely dependent on the community of stakeholders, and which are based on laws and often voluntary actions.
Johnson G. & Scholes H., 2000	Social responsibility is the detailed list of points for which an organization chooses to exceed its minimum obligations towards its various stakeholders.
Ferome G., 2000	Corporate social responsibility in France is based on the foundations of Anglo-Saxon business ethics, the rules of business ethics consist in codifying and implementing a certain number of procedures allowing the fluidity and efficiency of commercial and financial exchanges, without fundamentally challenging the liberal system.
Livre vert, 2001 (publié par la Commission Européenne en 2001)	The concept of corporate social responsibility essentially means that companies decide on their own initiative to contribute to improving society and making the environment cleaner.
Brahim L., 2001	Corporate social responsibility is expressed through three means of action: codes of good conduct, social labels and ethical investment practices. None of these three means is of any mandatory nature. The company's commitment is and remains voluntary. It is true that certain commercial or social pressures can sometimes constitute a constraint that is difficult to circumvent. In this case, the company is forced to adopt one or the other measure without it being possible to speak of an obligation in the legal sense of the term.
Triomphe C.E., 2002	Corporate social responsibility means voluntary taking on responsibilities that go beyond the application of laws and regulations.

Source : Tchankam Jean-Paul, Estay Christophe, « la pratique de la RS et ses implications dans l'entreprise », Gestion 2000, 2004, p35

2.3.Sustainable development and CSR

According to Brundtland's report (1987), "Our Common Future", published by the United Nations Commission on Environment and Development, sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to respond to theirs. This report emphasizes that the way in which organizations exploit the natural resources of our planet and the mode of consumption of modern life draw resources from our planet which could no longer produce more in the long term. As a result, this report insists on the urgency of taking into account the ecosystem of our planet (Baddache, 2010). In addition, it turns out that the countries of northern Europe are the countries most sensitive to the environmental and ecological cause (Guillon, 2004).

Public opinion is made aware of the challenges of sustainable development, in particular through media coverage of major economic scandals (Enron, Worldcom), the organization of earth summits on an international scale, and the implementation of sustainable development policies. The concept of sustainable development was born in the early 1970s following the Meadows Report, produced by a team of researchers from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology at the request of the Club of Rome, a think tank made up of economists, scientists, industrialists and civil servants from 53 countries.

The results of the report pointed the finger at economic growth deemed incompatible with environmental protection, showing the ecological dangers of the demographic and economic development experienced by the world during the post-war boom period. Then, in 1972, the United Nations conference on the human environment held in Stockholm laid the foundations of the "eco-development" concept, with the aim of integrating ecology and social equity into North-South economic development models (Leblanc and Baddache, 2015).

Thus, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) were created. After the first Stockholm Summit, the UN organized several ten-year "earth summits", the aim of which is to bring together and raise the awareness of leaders around sustainable development, in 1982 in Nairobi, in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, Johannesburg in 2002 and Rio de Janeiro again in 2012 (also known as Rio+20).

In the years that followed, the concept of sustainable development gained some momentum, especially following the activities of large humanitarian and environmental NGOs to raise public awareness of global warming, the depletion of natural resources, and the social and

human impact of globalization (“sweat factories” in supply chains, minerals from conflict zones, etc.). Major industrial accidents such as those of Seveso (1976), Chernobyl (1986), Deep Water Horizon (2010) or Rana Plaza (2013) have emphasized corporate social and environmental responsibility.

Sustainable development revolves around three pillars: economic, environmental, and social, and encourages us to review the challenges and priorities of globalization with the protection of the environment, the development of the population, and responsible economic growth (Leblanc and Baddache, 2015).

Thus, we can define the pillars of sustainable development as follows:

- The economy: encouraging economic growth and advocating responsible and sustainable modes of consumption and production;
- The environment: the protection of nature and the development of natural resources over the long term;
- Society: advocating social equity and satisfying human needs.

2.4. Responsible marketing and branding

Since its very first appearance, marketing has undergone constant evolution and change over time, which has generated several variables of the latter, including marketing said to be green, sustainable, or responsible. Sustainable marketing is a variation of marketing that includes the principles of relationship marketing and conventional marketing (Lichtle and Ferrandi, 2014) while taking into account the challenges of sustainable development, i.e. the social, ecological and ethics dimensions (Belz and Peattie, 2010).

Marketing also has an important role to play in the ecological dimension, through the integration of the principles of sustainable development in the marketing strategies of the company, from which comes the concept of responsible or sustainable marketing (Bascoul and Moutout, 2009).

Social or societal marketing is a variation of marketing which refers to all marketing actions whose purpose is to promote causes of general or social interest through the exploitation of the social values of the target to present the product of the company in a framework respectful of its consumer universe, it is mainly a question of finding a balance between making profits and respecting the well-being of consumers in the long term (Abratt and Sacks, 1988). Advertisers

(NGOs, associations, or others) defending a social cause can launch social marketing campaigns as can be launched by a company that wishes to promote responsible behavior on the part of consumers. Social marketing is also a social process through which individuals meet their needs in an ethical way that respects the environmental cause (Ramezainian et al., 2009).

Investing in social marketing campaigns means that the company in question supports a social, humanitarian or consumer health cause, its main objective here is not to sell its products or promote its services, but it will implicitly allow it to develop a positive institutional image in the eyes of the community, and consequently this positive image will be transferred to its products thereafter. Thus, the role of social marketing here is to influence consumer behavior (Andreasen, 1994).

In addition, the World Industrial Property Organization (WIPO) defines a trademark as “a sign which serves to differentiate identical or similar products or services offered by different producers or suppliers”. In a more conceptual and general way, the brand can be defined as the set of connotations, symbols and skills relating to a person, service, product or any other entity (Klein, 2000), which explains why nowadays brands have become important components of the economy and cultural accessories.

The brand image offers the company a major asset: its legitimacy. Indeed, the company derives its legitimacy through the public recognition of the values it claims (Kapferer, 2002).

Representing the trademark, the brand image can be defined in two ways. The first definition, in the proper sense of the term, concerns the graphic representation of qualities that an entity attributes to itself. In the figurative sense, the brand image includes all the judgments and feelings released regarding the latter and which forge its reputation.

Thus, the brand image is only valid through the validation of the opinion. Moreover, the brand image is closely linked to the visual methods of communication (Kapferer, 2002). The latter play a very important role in the regeneration and wear of the brand image, since they explicitly indicate the positioning of the company in its environment.

Thus, as Andreasen (1994) pointed out, social marketing plays a very important role: it influences consumer behavior. Therefore, very clear communication on the societal actions of the company and on the values it claims (Kapferer, 2002) will influence public opinion.

3. Empirical study

3.1. Lydec's CSR approach

Lydec is a Moroccan subsidiary of the French group Suez, created in 1995, which manages the distribution of water and electricity, the collection of wastewater and rainwater and public lighting for the inhabitants of the Greater Casablanca and Mohammedia Region, Morocco.

Lydec cares about the ecological dimension and undertakes societal actions for the good of the citizens of Casablanca. Thus, the Lydec Foundation was created. The Lydec Foundation intervenes in particular in the areas of the environment preservation, local solidarity and the societal commitment of employees. To this end, it defines and implements partnership projects with associations and institutional players.

It has also won various prizes and trophies, which shows just how committed Lydec is to sustainable and social development, including the "Top Performers CSR" trophy in 2018. It was recognized for the 5th consecutive time as the one of the "Top CSR Performers" in Morocco, awarded by the extra-financial rating agency Vigeo Eiris to the most successful companies in terms of social responsibility and sustainability risk management, and the Hassan II prize for the environment in 2018, the company was rewarded in the "Business Initiatives" category for its experimental urban agriculture project at the Médiouna wastewater treatment plant.

3.1.1. The Lydec SWOT matrix

Figure 1: The Lydec SWOT matrix

Source: Authors

- **Strengths :**

the online payment method is open to all Lydec customers with bank cards, Visa, Mastercard and CMI cards, registered for the Lydec online service through the company's website.

As for the mobile application, it provides 24/7 access to many services, such as paying bills, locating the nearest branch or payment point, access to latest news from Lydec, etc.

Lydec is well committed to sustainable development and has won several prizes and trophies for its ecological and societal actions.

- **Weaknesses:**

The rate of customer complaints is very high, especially with regard to water and electricity bills, which are considered rather expensive and exceed the amount of the “real” consumption of these dissatisfied customers.

- **Opportunities :**

Lydec enjoys a monopoly in the distribution of water and electricity in Casablanca – Mohamedia, and in the management of liquid sanitation services in the Greater Casablanca region, under a delegated management contract since 1997.

Lydec also contributes to the territorial development of Casablanca, and is actively involved in societal actions promoting its image as a socially responsible company.

- **Threats :**

Several cases of fraud are periodically recorded concerning the electricity service. These are households that use electricity cables illegally to avoid being billed.

The infrastructures are under development and the responsibilities for the water supply and sanitation policy are shared between several ministries, namely:

The ministry of energy, mines, water and the environment is responsible for the management of water resources and dams, The Ministry of the Interior, through its directorate of public utilities and concession services, is responsible for supervising the public utilities and concessions, and the water and sanitation directorate (DEA) from the same ministry assists municipalities with water and sanitation and plays an important role in the planning of water and sanitation infrastructure.

3.1.2. Analysis of the competitive position according to the PORTER 5+1 model

Figure 2: Lydec's PORTER model

Source: Authors

- **Competitive intensity:**

The water and electricity distribution sector is made up of 9 (indirect) competitors, of which REDAL and AMENDIS are the main competitors of Lydec given the importance of the areas they occupy.

- **Upstream pressure (suppliers) :**

The strong bargaining power of suppliers results from the fact that ONE is in a monopoly situation since it is the sole producer of water and electricity.

- **Downstream pressure (clients) :**

Les clients tirent leur pouvoir de négociation des syndicats et des associations du consommateur qui parlent de leurs droits et aussi de l'existence des produits de substitution.

- **Substitute products :**

For substitute products, drinking water can be replaced by mineral water because a very large number of households in Casablanca do not drink tap water. While we can have electricity through renewable energy.

- **Regulation :**

In Morocco, the prices of water, sanitation, and electricity are regulated. In the Greater Casablanca region, distribution tariffs are set by the Delegated Management Monitoring Committee, made up of the Ministry of the Interior.

- **New entrants :**

There is no risk of new entrants at the moment since there is regulation in terms of technical standards and Lydec benefits from a 30-year delegated management contract.

3.2.Methodological approach

Our study is part of an interpretative epistemological posture. This choice is justified by the fact that we want to identify and understand the perceptions and representations (Perret and Seville, 2003) that the population studied has in relation to the image of Lydec who practices CSR. In other words, we are interested in the reality of how the population under study interprets it. We have opted for inductive reasoning, given that we will obtain individual interpretations from each person interviewed, through semi-structured individual interviews.

The objective of this study is to assess the impact of practices included in Lydec's CSR framework on its brand image. To do this, it will first be necessary to assess the degree of knowledge of customers of this CSR approach, what are their perceptions and what opinion do they build on the company after learning about its societal and ecological actions. This is why we have chosen to follow a qualitative approach in our survey, in order to determine the degree of knowledge of Casablanca customers of the company's societal actions and to understand the image they forge of Lydec, especially knowing that it is a responsible company.

The qualitative approach provides insight into people's behavior and perceptions and allows their opinions on a particular topic to be explored in greater depth than in a survey, it generates insights and hypotheses that can contribute to understanding how an issue is perceived by the target population and makes it possible to define or identify the opinions related to a question. It is characterized by an approach that aims to describe and analyze the behaviors and points of view of the target population. It is based on a flexible and interactive search strategy.

We opted for semi-directive individual interviews which focus on the themes of sustainable development, CSR, and Lydec's CSR approach aimed at identifying the perceptions of the customers interviewed in Casablanca about the company. Moreover, it should be made clear that in the context of a qualitative study, it is not the size of the sample that matters, but it is the

quality, depth, richness and diversity of the interviews (Evrard and al, 2009). Indeed, it is about determining a minimum size, which makes it possible to obtain a certain confidence, while respecting the principle of saturation as well. Qualitative analysis consists of establishing the categories as the interviews are read until saturation of the categories is reached (Evrard and al, 2009). Thus, we continued these interviews until we reached data saturation (Glaser and Strauss, 1967), and we therefore stopped at a sample of 30 interviewed customers.

From the results of this analysis will be identified actions for improvement and recommendations for any possible shortcomings.

3.3.Results analysis

- **Theme 1: the composition of the study population**

In order to better understand the impact of Lydec's CSR approach on its brand image, we opted for a qualitative study based on interviews with a sample of 30 customers in the city of Casablanca. The target population contains more male respondents (56.7%) than female respondents (43.3%), with 17 male and 13 female respondents, their age group being mainly between 18 and 30 years old (46.7%), then between 31 and 40 years old (36.7%), and finally over 40 years old (16.7%).

Respondents mainly occupy civil servant positions (36.7%), liberal and similar professions come in second position (30%), then students come in third position (23.3%) and finally the unemployed (10%).

- **Theme 2: sustainable development and CSR**

We note that the majority of respondents (70%) attach great importance to social causes and environmental protection, and (23.3%) attach extreme importance to them. According to 90% of respondents, a socially engaged company is better than another company that is not. All respondents believe that companies must act to limit the excessive exploitation of natural resources and preserve the environment. This is now one of the responsibilities of companies.

The majority of respondents (80%) also claim that they adopt a lifestyle with responsible consumption and care about the ecological dimension. They affirm that CSR is of great importance for the economic and structural development of companies that practice it and are socially committed.

- **Theme 3: Lydec and its CSR approach**

A significant number of respondents (76.7%) are aware of the existence of the Lydec Foundation, which aims to defend social causes and operates within the framework of environmental protection. This means that the elements of our sample are aware that Lydec is a responsible company that operates in the protection of the environment and carries out actions for the benefit of society.

They also think that Lydec communicates well around its CSR approach and 23.3% of respondents think the opposite. The majority of respondents believe that Lydec is well committed to sustainable development. This reflects a positive opinion on the efforts made by Lydec to undertake these societal and ecological actions.

Most respondents have a positive opinion of Lydec's commitment and its CSR approach. For them, it initially reflects the solidarity and solidity of the brand, trust, and finally transparency, and more than 96% of respondents confirm that Lydec's CSR approach contributes to improving its reputation. It has a positive impact on the image of the company. According to the answers collected, we note that a good percentage of the people questioned have already heard of the Lydec Foundation or of the societal actions undertaken by the latter.

These are rather positive opinions collected around the CSR of Lydec, and thinking of it as a responsible company which has a sense of social responsibility and which contributes to the development of the Casablanca territory and the protection of the environment through its commitment regarding sustainable development.

As a result, it is clear that Lydec's CSR approach has significantly contributed to improving its image in the eyes of the citizens of Casablanca and has strengthened its reputation as a company that cares about social issues and not only about making profits.

3.4.Recommandations

We can summarize our recommendations as follows:

- Reinforce communication around the societal actions undertaken by Lydec since there were among our respondents those who had never heard of Lydec's societal commitment (7 respondents out of 30).
- Diversify the means of communication on the company's societal and ecological actions and highlight them on social networks.

- Publish more frequently and more regularly on the blog dedicated to Lydec news and the Lydec Foundation since the latter has been stagnating for some time, and to keep in touch with the company's customers interested in societal news and ecological.
- Organize competitive activities in schools to spread the culture of sustainable development among students and offer symbolic prizes to winners to increase Lydec's reputation as a responsible company.
- Sponsor activities in the higher education establishments (universities, business schools, etc.) to reflect a positive image of the company practicing CSR, and increase its notoriety.

4. Conclusion

Lydec as a socially responsible company is making considerable efforts to contribute to the social development of the city of Casablanca and the protection of the environment, through the Lydec Foundation, specially designed for this societal cause.

In order to better understand the impact of Lydec's CSR approach on the latter's brand image, we conducted a study which aims to analyze the perceptions of Casablanca customers regarding the CSR approach of Lydec.

According to the results obtained, Lydec's active commitment to sustainable development reflects a positive image of the company and contributes to improving its reputation as a responsible company, concerned about the social development of the city and the environmental Protection.

However, it is preferable that the company reinforces its communication around the societal actions that it undertakes and diversifies the means of communication used, since there were among our respondents those who have never heard of the societal commitment of Lydec.

It is also mandatory that it publishes more frequently and more regularly on the blog dedicated to the news of the Lydec Foundation, since the latter has been stagnant for some time, and to keep in touch with the company's customers interested in societal and ecological news.

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